

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF AMERICAN DYSTOPIA FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF TYPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

Demenko P.

*Postgraduate Student at the Department of Foreign Literature
Odesa I.I.Mechnikov National University
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2058-2094>*

Abstract

The article explores the phenomenon of American dystopia through the lens of the typological method of analysis. The research relies on a historical periodization of the development of dystopian discourse in literary studies, within which three main stages are identified. The first stage (1960s–1970s) focused on comprehending the essence of dystopia as an independent genre and on tracing its historical genesis. The second stage (1980s) involved attempts to define dystopia's position among other literary phenomena, particularly within the framework of science fiction, utopia, and social satire. The third stage (1990s to the present) is characterized by interest in the internal poetics of the genre, its themes, artistic means, and transformations within new cultural contexts. The article identifies the key traits of contemporary American dystopia, including a departure from the postmodern paradigm, a critical rethinking of classical models, growing interest in gender issues, bioethics, artificial reproduction, and the emergence of a new type of protagonist. To illustrate current trends in American dystopian writing, the study references works such as Sandra Newman's *Julia*, Chuck Palahniuk's *Adjustment Day*, and Veronica Roth's *Divergent*. These examples demonstrate the renewal of the genre through themes of control, individualism, informational influence, and identity transformation. The article contributes to a deeper understanding of the dynamics of American dystopia in today's cultural field.

Keywords: dystopia, genre evolution, totalitarianism, social protest, identity search, intertextuality.

The most dangerous, and sometimes even inevitable processes occurring in society, from a futuristic or prognostic point of view, are usually reflected in the literary genre of «dystopia». Modern dystopia, as foreign researchers mainly call works of this genre, has undergone a rather noticeable evolutionary path during the twentieth century, and a significant textual array of corresponding works has been created in various national literatures.

The definition of the concept of «dystopia» is debatable, as evidenced by scientific and critical research by literary scholars, such as: S.V. Bezchotnikova, Yu.S. Gavrykova, G.V. Glodzia, Yu.A. Zhadanova, M.V. Ikonnikova, J. Keiteba, O.M. Nikolenko, S.G. Shishkina and others.

The term «dystopia», as is known, was first defined and substantiated in the work of R. Negley and M. Patrick's «The Quest for Utopia», 1952, which identified three main features that distinguish artistic utopia from other literary forms, also noted the «negative» or «satirical nature of utopia».

Systematic research in the field of dystopia is conventionally divided into three stages in the history of studying this phenomenon, which correspond to three main areas of research, rightly highlighted by M. V. Ikonnikova: «1) consideration of this genre in a non-literary context as a reflection of historical reality or ideology; 2) analysis of the relationship of the dystopian novel with other literary phenomena; 3) research aimed at creating a theoretical model of the genre, that is, such a characteristic of the type of artistic whole that would explain its functioning» [1, p.142].

Social ideologies, technological myths, ecological ethics, mechanization, robotization, techno and cyber progress, digital state, AI - at each stage of real historical time can serve as a source of dystopia. These extra-literary, historical factors provoke the emergence of

dystopias of the first direction, which we will define as social.

Speaking of human nature, morality, we attach greater importance to objective factors and subjective attitude to the environment. The subjectivity of perception of reality is associated with hope, aspirations and goals that concern the whole society and its development, that is, utopian consciousness. Utopia is a traditional form of consciousness, but in the twentieth century modernized directions were born on its basis - a superstructure of romantic reflection, which, although they touch on social life, are quite transcendental in relation to it - these are fantasy and dystopia. The attempt to combine social analysis and moral issues, in our opinion, causes the genre diffusion of dystopia, makes it an open genre form.

The dystopian genre has traditions that are completely different from other genres, and its political, social and philosophical components determine the relevance and popularity of this genre among a wide range of readers.

The First World War and revolutionary transformations became a powerful source for the development of dystopian ideas in literature, when people tried to embody the ideals of utopia in real life and create a just society - this was the impetus for the formation and development of dystopia.

1960-1970s. we consider the first stage, characterized by a surge in research on dystopia in foreign literary studies, cultural studies, and philosophy. During this period, dystopia is primarily concerned with the problem of understanding negative models of the socio-political system. The works of C. Walsh, M. Kvapien, J. Keiteb, F. Polak, N. Fry, A. Schein, and others highlight the socio-cultural aspect of dystopia and emphasize its ideological content. The famous philosophers G. Marcuse, L. Mumford, and H. Ortega y Gasset made

their contribution to the interpretation of dystopian discourse. In our opinion, it is important to dwell on the work of the Canadian scholar N. Fry. He defines the term «dystopia» as «utopian satire», which is unlike anything else, the emergence of which is due to the development of the modern technical environment, which has taken possession not only of the fate of nature, but also of man [4, p. 56]. American researcher J. Keiteb criticizes utopia, identifying three temporal problems in it: «1) utopia is unable to show the way to everyone from the real world to the world that reflects its ideology; 2) even if the future desired for utopia is achieved, it will not be able to provide it with anything other than a way to establish strict control over the thoughts and actions of those who are happy; 3) utopian dreams in practice turn out to be threatening to man» [3, p. 36], which, accordingly, causes the emergence of negative utopia, that is, dystopia. J. Keiteb and F. Polak, analyzing the phenomenon of dystopia in literature, argue that «it appeared as a result of the First World War and the Russian experiment, then the Second World War and the rule of the dictatorships of Mussolini, Hitler, Stalin» [5, p.65]. So, based on the analysis of the above-mentioned studies, we state that dystopia arises as a response to the crisis of utopian ideals, social ideologies, as a gap between the individual dream and the ideology of the real world.

At the second stage – the 1980s – the subject of research is determining the place of dystopia among other literary phenomena (Yu. Kagarlytsky, K. Kumar, V. Chalykova). One of the priority directions in the study of dystopia of this period is its understanding as a type of science fiction, depicting events of the future using technical inventions (L. Sargent). Sometimes dystopia was also considered as «anti-communist fiction» (using this term also in the sense of – unrelated to the ideology of anti-communism). From this point of view, socialism was reflected by D. M. Perry in the novel «The Scarlet Kingdom» (1908), and later by O. Huxley» [2, p. 218]. The works that were mainly written in the 20s-30s of the 20th century were studied. G. Sabat notes that the concept of «dystopia» was also considered as a critical view of progress [3, p. 113]. Another concept is proposed – «countertopia», which is interpreted as «negative utopia», which at the same time contains a positive meaning. Countertopia is defined «not simply as a dispute with utopia, but as its fundamental denial. Denial of the very possibility of building an ideal society (as the implementation of the idea of social progress and the desired orientation towards the realization of a utopian ideal that would have a generally significant character» [5, p.64]. In our opinion, it is at this stage that the genre of dystopia from utopia is completely separated, since there is already a significant dystopian textual mass, and attempts are made to theoretically comprehend and define the concept of dystopian discourse.

It is worth noting that at this time the substantive and formal characteristics of the classical dystopia are being formed: 1) the presence of a negative futuristic model of society in the form of a totalitarian state hostile to man. 2) the instability of the dystopian world, its potential mobility, which determines its perception as a

possibility. 3) anthropocentricity, which implies a shift in emphasis from the image of society to the image of man. 4) the presence of a hero bent on rebellion, who is in opposition to the state system and the conflict between the individual and the state. 5) the situation of a pseudo-carnival, the basis of which is a kind of inversion of carnival elements - theatricalization of action, ambivalence (fear and reverence for power), the elimination of public and power regalia, which turns into the surveillance of everyone by everyone. 6) the ritualization of life, which implies the inviolability of the established daily schedule for citizens of the dystopian state, the daily repetition of which resembles the cyclical nature of a ritual. 7) a story in the form of a diary, which is evidence of the formation of personal consciousness in dystopia. Thus, the dystopia genre becomes closer to works of science fiction and post-apocalyptic, which is due to the rapid technical development and its impact on people's lives. Dream novels are followed by warning novels, where the writer presents to the public his interpretation of the further path of development of civilization. The victory of the machine order and control over man, shown by dystopia, is a warning for a society that ceases to consider man the pinnacle of creation, which leads to the loss and leveling of moral values and the spiritual enslavement of humanity. Functionally, at this stage, dystopia combines 2 components: it becomes a response to the processes of the present and is a certain scenario of the future.

The main characteristic of the third stage – 1990-2000s – is the turn to studying the specifics of the dystopian genre, its problems and poetics (O. Vorobyova, O. Lazarenko, B. Lanin, O. Nikolenko, O. Pavlova, A. Tymofeeva, V. Chalykova, S. Shishkina, L. Yuryeva), understanding dystopia as an artistic system, its structure and functions (O. Yevchenko, M. Ikonnikova, V. Kucher, E. Martynova, G. Sabat, I. Tuzovsky, M. Shadursky). During this period, studies devoted to the dystopia of the second half of the 20th century appear (S. Bezchotnikova, A. Grigorovska, Yu. Zhadanov, O. Kopach, A. Timofeeva), where dystopia, preserving and developing the traditions of its classical model, acquires new features, such as: 1) increased anthropocentricity. The image of the protagonist, often a bearer of reformist ideas, becomes more complicated and presented in development, the inner world of the individual is revealed more deeply. 2) minimal detachment from real time. Dystopias of the second half of the 20th century. are addressed equally to both the future and the present, the boundaries of dystopia and reality are blurred. The modern dystopia serves not so much as a forecast of the future, but rather as a kind of chronicle of contemporary reality. 3) a relatively optimistic tone, compared to the tragic hopelessness of dystopias of the beginning of the century. In many works of this genre of the second half of the 20th century. the situation of enslavement by civilization does not seem hopeless, the process of liberation struggle against the new totalitarian system mostly leads to the desired result - the hero manages to escape. 4) intertextuality, which is realized in the use of parody techniques, the presence of numerous similar images-functions, repeated motifs, plot moves, etc. The analysis of these features suggests that

dystopias of the second half of the 20th century evolve within the framework of the postmodern paradigm, employing its aesthetic strategies. These, in turn, contribute to the dismantling of the tragic tone characteristic of classical dystopian literature.

In contrast to the dystopia of the 1920s–1930s, in which the artistic technique of depersonalization of the personality with the characteristic absence of descriptions of the appearance, personal characteristics of the character, feelings, sensations (numerology of E. Zamiatin, onomasticon of «eloquent names» of O. Huxley, etc.) was actively used as the main method of creating the image of the hero (the anthropological dimension of the human image is deepened in the dystopia of the second half of the 20th century). The increased anthropocentricity of the dystopia of the second half of the 20th century implies a departure from depersonalization and a shift in emphasis to the individualization of the personality.

This process of individualization of the characters' images, the tendency to blur the boundaries between dystopian fictional reality and actual reality, as well as the development of dystopia in terms of moving away from the postmodernist paradigm, which involves rethinking the traditions of the classics, is a feature of modern dystopia, that is, we are talking about the fourth stage of development, which continues today, that is, the first quarter of the 21st century. If the image of the hero of dystopia of the third period simultaneously inherited the aesthetic canons of romanticism (individualism, rebelliousness); naturalism (the conditioning of behavioral characteristics by the instinct of self-preservation, awareness of the problem of heredity through gender issues, construction of the structure of the story according to the principle of a «human document»); modernism (emphasis on the intrinsic value of the character's personality, his inner world, motives of loneliness and alienation, the gender component of human images); existentialism (emphasis on the search for inner freedom and meaning of existence, the ability to overcome the absurdity of being (rebellion, escape), the presence of borderline situations), then modern dystopia adds to the listed features a postmodern component of the character and reality characteristics. The social community of people, often described by authors in a deadlock situation, the rhizomatic depiction of reality, the unreliability of the narrative and fragmentation generate a feeling of uncertainty and anxiety in the reader. At the same time, the deadlock itself can be technological, political and economic. The development of technical means has led to the development of artificial intelligence, robotics, thanks to which it is possible to establish total control over society - to track the slightest movements that deviate from the norm, which allows you to destroy dissenters at the very beginning.

As a result, we observe that individuals are deprived of their right to inner freedom, the freedom of critical thinking, and the ability to assess what is happening around them. Absolute conformism is systematically instilled, while nonconformity and clearly prescribed protocol-based behavior are enforced—any deviation from which is regarded as a severe offense. The authors derive their conclusions and observations from

reality, illustrating societal transformations prompted by various conflicts. However, these reflections are not confined solely to real-life contexts but are also intertwined with elements of fantasy and science fiction. This combination serves to highlight the absurdity, illogicality, and hostility of the world toward the human being. At the current stage, dystopian literature increasingly addresses gender issues, human cloning and artificial reproduction, mutations, and the relationship between humans and robot-companions or assistants. In our view, a new type of protagonist emerges in 21st-century dystopia. The classical dystopian hero undergoes a transformation, grounded in a shift in the form of rebellion or protest. Already in the second half of the 20th century, social protest gradually gives way to a personal, existential one—no longer aimed at enacting revolutionary change, but at attaining inner freedom.

Thus, in contemporary dystopia, the outcome of rebellion becomes secondary to its philosophical essence, which defines the trajectory of one's search for identity. The schematic character types of classical dystopia, which formed a closed narrative structure, are replaced by an «open» character model that reflects an unfinished type of hero (in Mikhail Bakhtin's terms) of the late 20th century—a postmodern figure. This in turn determines the openness of the modern dystopian novel's form. Whereas the relatively optimistic endings typical of late 20th-century dystopias often allowed the protagonist to escape the totalitarian system and secure their own future, in the contemporary dystopian narrative, such outcomes are increasingly replaced by the imposition of a «predetermined paradise»—a state of human dependency on the technogenic and digital world.

This is exactly what Sandra Newman's novel «Julia» is - a feminist version of Orwell's cult novel «1984». In the center of the plot, instead of Winston Smith, there is Julia, who is described much less in Orwell.

Julia Worthing is not only Winston Smith's lover, she is an intelligent, determined, complex person. Her job as a mechanic in the Fiction Department of the Ministry of Truth is to service the machines that create propaganda texts. She understands that the world around her is not perfect, she knows how the truth is falsified, she analyzes everything that happens, draws conclusions, but does not fight openly.

In fact, it might be time for her to give up sexcrime altogether. Better to live out her life in chastity... than to have another tryst or two, then an agonizing death in the bowels of Love. [6, p. 92]

Why was the damned man always complaining? He was as well off as one could be without being Inner Party. And all his talk of abolishing the Party was the purest vanity. [6, p. 116]

The interaction between women plays an important role in the plot of the novel. Julia, facing problems, finds support from other women, she is not alone, which is a reflection of the idea of feminist solidarity and the importance of support among women, which, in turn, reduces the tragedy.

Her coworker Essie took over the heavy work, as Julia had done for her in the past, and even gave Julia two moth-eaten aspirins from her own supply. [6, p. 81]

Chuck Palahniuk offers his version of a dystopian society in the 2018 dystopian novel «Adjustment Day».

Analyzing and observing events in modern America, its present, the novel can be considered predictive. The author depicts US society, which has split into three states after mass clashes caused by radical ideas. After the coup, the country is divided along lines of race, gender and sexual orientation, establishing a new order.

«Talbot's plan mimicked Ellison's by requiring Southern states to be united as a single nation, to be occupied exclusively by people of African descent. The remaining states would be reserved exclusively for citizens of European ancestry. With the exception of California—the Sunshine State would be set aside for a special purpose.» [7, p. 118]

This novel predicted events in the United States in 2025, when political tension, social inequality, and the struggle for minority rights are growing.

In January 2025, the People March took place in the United States, where thousands of people came out to protest Donald Trump's policies on women's rights, the LGBT+ community, and the environment. The future, which Chuck Palahniuk predicted 7 years ago in «Correction Day» has become a reality that resembles the mass movement in the work, where people also protested against the existing order.

A similar dystopian novel is «Divergent» by the American writer Veronica Roth. In «Divergent,» the structure of dystopia is clearly traced through the depiction of the structure of a totalitarian society: a complex system of rigorous training and psychological tests is described, aimed at making a person a «manageable being.» But the system fails when «divergents» appear - people with a «different» consciousness, with a special worldview. They cannot, due to their innate properties, become «cogs» in the totalitarian machine.

«Every faction conditions its members to think and act a certain way. And most people do it. For most people, it's not hard to learn, to find a pattern of thought that works and stay that way... but our minds move in a dozen different directions. We can't be confined to one way of thinking, and that terrifies our leaders. It means we can't be controlled. And it means that no matter what they do, we will always cause trouble for them.» [8, p. 181]

Militaristic spirit, unconventional thinking, caste society – these are the traditional features of the real world, without which dystopia cannot do. However, unusual for it is the philosophy of hope, which is interconnected and conditioned by the concept of social progress. The heroes of the novel associate their aspirations, first of all, with the change and destruction of the unacceptable social order. This philosophy becomes a powerful source of the search for truth. Truth does not exist outside of good. In the model of the world built by man, which is based on the category of «truth», evil can never win a decisive victory; If there are victories, then they are temporary, which, in the end, turn out to be

fictitious, illusory and, therefore, unstable. The Achilles heel of evil is that it cannot be independent, cannot be primordial – there is always a cause that gives rise to it. As is known, the cause can be eliminated. The main feature of evil is the concept of «causes»:

«Human reason can excuse any evil; that is why it's so important that we don't rely on it.» [8, p. 45].

Unlike evil, good is independent and ungrounded—and thus, evil is ontologically powerless before it.

The plot of almost any work in the dystopian genre is the confrontation of an individual with an entire system of totalitarian control. In the novel by V. Roth, a teenage girl becomes such a «divergent» that she counteracts the system. This novel has a didactic character and forms the empathy of a fairly young readership.

Thus, we state that the term «dystopia» is a rather complex phenomenon. Each historical period has its own vision. Having analyzed the main features of dystopia of the first and second half of the 20th century, we found that the following mandatory components are characteristic of classical dystopia: the presence of a cruel totalitarian society, the variability of the perception of dystopian society, anthropocentrism, the conflict of the clash between the hero and the totalitarian society, the situation of a pseudo-carnival, the ritualization of life, the narrative in the form of a diary. In the second half, along with the constant elements, new ones appear: the emphasis of the study shifts from the totalitarian state to the inner world of man, a close connection with real time, a reflection of modern processes, the hero's victory over the totalitarian world, which is expressed in escape, the use of postmodern techniques (intertextuality). In the dystopia of the second half, there is a new type of hero, his social protest is replaced by a personal one, what is significant is not the result of the rebellion, but its philosophical content, which determines the vector of the hero's search for his own identity, an open form of the image, which reflects the unfinished type of hero. For the dystopia of the 21st century, a characteristic feature is genre diffusion, which blurs the genre forms of the work, philosophical and ontological problems of human existence, his confrontation with the world of robots and AI, a new type of hero, an optimistic finale, which is manifested in the hero's escape beyond the boundaries of totalitarian society, also becomes innovative for dystopias.

We see prospects for further development in establishing the typological weaknesses of the modern dystopian novel and a more in-depth analysis of the above texts by American authors.

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